

DIARRHEA

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Annotation: Diarrhea — loose, watery and possibly more-frequent bowel movements — is a common problem. It may be present alone or be associated with other symptoms, such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain or weight loss.

Key words: vomiting, abdominal pain, food allergies, weight loss, infections, bloating, blood test, stool test, hydrogen breath test, colonoscopy, treatment, biopsy, antibiotics.

Introduction:

Diarrhea — loose, watery and possibly more-frequent bowel movements — is a common problem. It may be present alone or be associated with other symptoms, such as nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain or weight loss. Luckily, diarrhea is usually short-lived, lasting no more than a few days. Causes of diarrhea: food allergies and intolerances, some infections, digestive tract problems, abdominal surgery and long time use of medicines.

Symptoms of diarrhea: Abdominal cramps or pain, bloating, nausea, vomiting, fever, blood in the stool, mucus in the stool, urgent need to have a bowel movement.

Diagnosis: Your doctor will ask about your medical history, review the medications you take, conduct a physical exam and may order tests to determine what's causing your diarrhea. Possible tests include:

Blood test. A complete blood count test, measurement of electrolytes and kidney function tests can help indicate the severity of your diarrhea

Stool test. Your doctor might recommend a stool test to see if a bacterium or parasite is causing your diarrhea.

Hydrogen breath test. This type of test can help your doctor determine if you have a lactose intolerance. After you drink a liquid that contains high levels of lactose, your doctor measures the amount of hydrogen in your breath at regular intervals. Breathing out too much hydrogen indicates that you aren't fully digesting and absorbing lactose.

Flexible sigmoidoscopy or colonoscopy. Using a thin, lighted tube that's inserted in your rectum, your doctor can see inside your colon. The device is also equipped with a tool that allows your doctor to take a small sample of tissue

(biopsy) from your colon. Flexible sigmoidoscopy provides a view of the lower colon, while colonoscopy allows the doctor to see the entire colon.

Upper endoscopy. Doctors use a long, thin tube with a camera on the end to examine your stomach and upper small intestine. They may remove a tissue sample (biopsy) for analysis in the laboratory.

Most diarrhea in children is caused by viruses. Diarrhea can also be caused by bacteria, parasites, changes in diet (such as drinking too much fruit juice), problems with the intestines (such as allergy to foods), and the use of some medicines. Here are some ways to help prevent diarrhea: Stop germs from spreading. has signs of dehydration, such as crying with few or no tears, having a dry mouth or cracked lips, feeling dizzy or lightheaded, acting very sleepy or less alert, has a high fever, has blood in their poop, has diarrhea that doesn't better after several days.

Treatment of diarrhea: most cases of acute diarrhea clear on their own within a couple of days without treatment. If you've tried lifestyle changes and home remedies for diarrhea without success, your doctor might recommend medications or other treatments. Antibiotics or anti-parasitic medications might help treat diarrhea caused by bacteria or parasites.

If a virus is causing your diarrhea, an or children, ask your doctor about using an oral rehydration solution, such as Pedialyte, to prevent dehydration or replace lost fluids. antibiotics won't help.

Conclusion: To treat or prevent dehydration, give your child liquids that contain electrolytes. You can also give your child an oral rehydration solution, such as Pedialyte, Naturalyte, Infalyte, or CeraLyte, as directed. Talk to a doctor about giving these solutions to your infant.